

Image Report: Densitometria TAUE10

C:\Users\Giusy\OneDrive - Università degli Studi di Verona\GRIBA labs\PROGETTI\Progetto Tau (AC-AV-MGB)\Risultati\TAU_ESP_6_PTB E10\PCR TAU 10\Densitometria TAUE10.scn

Acquisition Information

Program	cSeries
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Image Information

Acquisition Date	unknown
User Name	Andrea Corsi
Image Area (mm)	X: 270.9 Y: 203.2
Pixel Size (µm)	X: 84.7 Y: 84.7
Data Range (Int)	6 - 55483

Analysis Settings

Detection	Lane detection: Automatically detected lanes Band detection:
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	Bands detected with different sensitivity per lane Manually adjusted bands Lane Background Subtraction: Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59 Lane width: 8.97 mm
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Lane Statistics

Lane No.	Adj. Total Band Vol. (Int)	Total Band Vol. (Int)	Adj. Total Lane Vol. (Int)	Total Lane Vol. (Int)	Bkgd. Vol. (Int)	Norm. Factor
1	N/A	N/A	317.709.560	549.303.024	231.593.464	N/A
2	N/A	N/A	16.279.162	219.908.978	203.629.816	N/A
3	N/A	N/A	55.967.788	242.926.030	186.958.242	N/A
4	73.242.184	92.415.252	114.822.910	299.173.446	184.350.536	N/A
5	63.591.838	84.976.066	110.538.708	297.059.806	186.521.098	N/A
6	56.912.036	79.916.368	100.031.140	303.689.258	203.658.118	N/A
7	N/A	N/A	291.472.758	511.565.646	220.092.888	N/A
8	N/A	N/A	9.693.064	205.308.962	195.615.898	N/A
9	N/A	N/A	55.781.652	238.836.232	183.054.580	N/A
10	82.151.484	102.259.896	128.309.820	306.049.454	177.739.634	N/A
11	88.478.942	108.894.118	152.073.218	330.213.532	178.140.314	N/A
12	81.371.218	106.218.466	123.084.974	330.718.940	207.633.966	N/A
13	N/A	N/A	319.008.272	543.169.652	224.161.380	N/A
14	N/A	N/A	12.378.892	201.845.200	189.466.308	N/A
15	N/A	N/A	90.037.142	264.370.784	174.333.642	N/A
16	113.585.678	137.167.604	153.828.048	322.517.084	168.689.036	N/A
17	100.181.978	124.864.502	152.000.714	329.317.832	177.317.118	N/A
18	109.960.690	136.267.452	160.935.772	355.418.848	194.483.076	N/A
19	N/A	N/A	273.387.038	471.407.652	198.020.614	N/A

Lane And Band Analysis

Lane 1

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 2

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 3

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 4

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,642	70.841.390	86.187.116	N/A	N/A	96,7	61,7
2		N/A	0,798	2.400.794	6.228.136	N/A	N/A	3,3	2,1

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 5

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,641	59.284.316	75.381.052	N/A	N/A	93,2	53,6
2		N/A	0,797	4.307.522	9.595.014	N/A	N/A	6,8	3,9

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 6

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,645	51.848.628	68.510.980	N/A	N/A	91,1	51,8
2		N/A	0,798	5.063.408	11.405.388	N/A	N/A	8,9	5,1

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 7

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 8

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 9

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
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Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 10

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,680	78.287.254	93.310.846	N/A	N/A	95,3	61,0
2		N/A	0,819	3.864.230	8.949.050	N/A	N/A	4,7	3,0

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 11

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,684	82.540.186	97.390.256	N/A	N/A	93,3	54,3
2		N/A	0,823	5.938.756	11.503.862	N/A	N/A	6,7	3,9

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 12

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,684	73.604.598	91.168.056	N/A	N/A	90,5	59,8
2		N/A	0,825	7.766.620	15.050.410	N/A	N/A	9,5	6,3

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 13

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 14

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 15

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 16

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,692	106.207.018	123.879.126	N/A	N/A	93,5	69,0
2		N/A	0,853	7.378.660	13.288.478	N/A	N/A	6,5	4,8

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 17

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,693	90.847.406	107.744.124	N/A	N/A	90,7	59,8
2		N/A	0,860	9.334.572	17.120.378	N/A	N/A	9,3	6,1

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 18

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %
1		N/A	0,700	98.833.658	116.534.280	N/A	N/A	89,9	61,4
2		N/A	0,869	11.127.032	19.733.172	N/A	N/A	10,1	6,9

Band Detection	Automatically detected bands with custom sensitivity: 100
Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm

Lane 19

Band No.	Band Label	Mol. Wt. (KDa)	Relative Front	Adj. Volume (Int)	Volume (Int)	Abs. Quant.	Rel. Quant.	Band %	Lane %

Lane Background	Lane background subtracted with disk size: 59
Lane Width	8.97 mm